

Multi-Connectivity Enhancements for the 6G era

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Abstract—In the dawn of 6G and the stupendous use cases it is anticipated to support, the ever-growing requisites for higher data rates and ultra-reliable low latency communications (URLLC) stipulate ubiquitous and robust connectivity. In this direction, architectural enhancements beyond the existing 3GPP-based 5G-Advanced specifications are deemed indispensable. The multi-connectivity domain is a cornerstone in this architectural evolution, laying the ground for technology convergence, and rendering resilient, high-performing, and energy-efficient communications. This work seeks to unveil the various multi-connectivity methods available in standards and propose new paths in this area, envisioning the network architecture evolution in the 6G era. Some new, innovative, multi-access solutions are presented, shedding light on the multi-connectivity aspects envisioned in 3GPP Rel-20 and beyond. In particular, this paper emphasizes on the envisaged use cases necessitating multi-access connectivity, and delineates how Access Traffic Steering, Switching, and Splitting (ATSSS) functionality can be further optimized to support the imminent demand. Based on this request, current work proposes ATSSS enhancements entailing the use of the QUIC protocol to convey NAS signalling over non-3GPP access networks (*QUIC for NAS over Non-3GPP*), as well as an alternative to the legacy ATSSS which enables direct communication between the User Equipment (UE) and the network, by eliminating the use of N3IWF on the non-3GPP access path (*ATSSS with Offloaded Non-3GPP Access*). Finally, we propose potential extensions in the ATSSS functionality to support UE's connectivity over two 3GPP access networks, while maintaining its connection over the non-3GPP access path (*DualSteer*). Such kind of architectural enhancements to provide capacity aggregation and incessant connectivity, are expected to be the norm in 6G networks, so that the extreme demands of the upcoming applications can be sufficiently satisfied.

Keywords—Multi-Connectivity; QUIC; NAS signalling; ATSSS-OF; DualSteer;

I. INTRODUCTION

Global alliances for the development of 6G, such as the NGMN, the GSMA, the ITU, the 6G SNS-ICE which is the European initiative, as well as global standardization bodies such as 3GPP, have invested tremendous human and monetary effort in identifying the use cases and designing the roadmap for the next generation of mobile networks; the 6G. The most representative use cases to be supported by future (6G) networks [1], revolve around the areas of collaborative robots, immersive experience, trusted environments, physical

awareness, digital twins, and ultimately, a fully connected world. To satisfy the requirements imposed by such diverse use cases, future networks are forced to be highly adaptive and fulfil the extreme throughput and deterministic ultra-low latency communication needs, while simultaneously staying robust and resilient, offering ubiquitous connectivity.

Under such circumstances, an everywhere- and always-available high-performing network is the only way forward for future 6G networks. To realize this “fully connected world”, 5G-Advanced has already laid the foundation by enhancing the existing multi-connectivity options, which are expected to be further optimized and extended to support the extraordinary future demands. 6G technology is expected to build upon and further enhance the existing 5G-Advanced features, rather than providing a totally different architecture, as many global alliances and operators have clearly stated [2][3].

To support the ever-increasing throughput demand, bandwidth aggregation is deemed necessary. This aggregation may be realized through existing techniques, such as *Carrier Aggregation* (leveraging advances in MIMO, beamforming, and advanced modulation techniques), or via *Multi-Radio Dual Connectivity*, or even *ATSSS* functionality. Each of these techniques is based on different principles, having their own pros and cons. These techniques are constantly enhanced, with 3GPP standardizing their advancements in each Release.

While Carrier Aggregation (CA) [4][5] and Multi-Radio Dual Connectivity (MR-DC) [6] are mainly Radio Access Network (RAN) related techniques involving low-layer protocol control information exchange, ATSSS controls the communication between the mobile device and the network at session level, using RAN as a means to transparently convey session-related control information to the Core Network (CN), using the so-called Non-Access Stratum (NAS) signalling. ATSSS, as specified up until 3GPP Rel-18 [7][8], is enabling a mobile device to communicate with the network, simultaneously over one 3GPP and one non-3GPP access path, i.e., 5G NR and WLAN, respectively. This feature exploits the existence of multiple interfaces in modern mobile handsets along with the multipath extensions of well-known protocols (i.e., MPTCP, MPQUIC), to aggregate bandwidth, thus increase throughput and minimize delays, while providing seamless connectivity and resilience in case of failures or user mobility.

Some advancements in the multi-connectivity domain, and more specifically in the ATSSS functionality, are presented within this paper, contributing to an enhanced network

architecture in the 6G realm. The first enhancement proposed through this work, is the use of the QUIC protocol to convey NAS signalling over the non-3GPP access path, optimizing and simplifying the network procedures by minimizing excessive signalling, while preserving network’s control over the mobile device via the non-3GPP access path. QUIC protocol has been specified by IETF [9] and is considered the de-facto transport layer protocol to convey HTTP/3 application traffic. A second enhancement is an alternative solution to the legacy ATSSS architecture, named *ATSSS-OF*, which eliminates the use of N3IWF on the non-3GPP access path, and enables direct communication between the UE and the network by exploiting QUIC protocol’s multipath extensions (MPQUIC). Finally, our current work proposes a candidate solution which is based on and extends ATSSS allowing a mobile device to be simultaneously connected to a single or two different Public Land Mobile Networks (PLMNs) over two 3GPP access networks, and one additional non-3GPP access, on the basis of *DualSteer* study which has recently commenced within 3GPP [10]. By enabling a mobile device to be simultaneously connected to and exchange traffic over three paths (i.e., one 5G NR TN, one 5G NR NTN, and a WLAN), we are contributing to the network evolution towards the 6G-envisioned ubiquitous connectivity.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II is illustrating some key 6G use cases, which have been identified within 3GPP and are requesting for multi-access network enhancements in order to be realized. Section III provides an overview of the current (3GPP Rel-18) ATSSS functionality and presents the details of the alternative ATSSS-Offloaded (ATSSS-OF) architecture. Section IV emphasizes on our proposed optimization to leverage QUIC for conveying NAS signalling over non-3GPP access, illustrating a candidate control plane protocol stack. In Section V we propose a *DualSteer* solution, realizing the convergence of the different technologies to provide seamless and enhanced connectivity to future mobile devices. Section VI revolves around the technical realization of ATSSS, indicating state-of-art packet scheduling algorithms in the field. Finally, Section VII concludes this work and identifies future directions and advancements towards 6G network architecture.

II. MULTI-ACCESS USE CASES

In the context of Rel-19 (5G-Advanced), 3GPP Working Group 1 (aka SA1) has identified the use cases necessitating dual-3GPP access connectivity [11], preparing essentially the ground for 6G, where the network is expected to be available everywhere, always, and for everyone. We selected to present the most representative use cases, to stress the significant role multi-connectivity is anticipated to play within the future mobile architecture.

Affordable satellite access is expected to be the norm in future mobile networks, so that seamless connectivity is guaranteed. In this direction, one salient use case is depicted in *Figure 1*, where the mobile handset is connected to an anchor PLMN (i.e., PLMN-1) simultaneously over a NR TN and over NR-NTN; the latter belonging to a different PLMN (i.e., PLMN-2). This way, throughput aggregation, traffic differentiation, and resilient connectivity can be realized.

Figure 1: Dual 3GPP access (VPN traffic) plus concurrent single-access data session (non-VPN)

Another use case emphasizes on the need to support seamless transition between dual-3GPP access operation and ATSSS-based operation. This requirement arises when coverage of one of the two 3GPP accesses becomes poor or unavailable, while a non-3GPP access link is available. *Figure 2* and *Figure 3* illustrate how a mobile device should be able to seamlessly operate when moving from outdoor to indoor environments and vice versa.

Figure 2: Outdoor Multi-Connectivity use case – two 3GPP access networks

Figure 3: Indoor Multi-Connectivity use case – one 3GPP and one non-3GPP access network

A final use case depicted in *Figure 4*, presents the critical role satellites in different orbits are expected to play in the interworking with terrestrial networks; this is how ubiquitous connectivity is envisioned in 6G.

Figure 4: Inter-PLMN scenario, with terrestrial and multiple non-terrestrial coverage

III. ATSSS FUNCTIONALITY

As stated earlier, throughput requirements are constantly increasing with each new generation of mobile networks, along with advanced applications' demands. To satisfy the higher-throughput and lower-latency pressure, various aggregation techniques and multi-connectivity options remain in focus of many research institutions and standardization bodies, being perpetually optimized. Some well-established aggregation techniques, such as the Carrier Aggregation and the Multi-Radio Dual Connectivity, are expected to remain competitive also in 6G networks due to their continuous enhancements and broad adoption. However, since these techniques have been extensively studied in literature, and are Radio Access Network (RAN)-oriented, we instead selected to concentrate our focus on Core Network techniques and their evolution towards 6G. ATSSS is the only Core Network multi-connectivity technique, allowing a multihomed mobile device to be connected to the 5GC over a 3GPP (i.e., 5G NR) and over a non-3GPP (i.e., WLAN) access network simultaneously.

A. Access Traffic Steering, Switching, and Splitting (ATSSS)

Contrary to Carrier Aggregation and Multi-Radio Dual Connectivity techniques which have radio access impact and may induce excessive signalling, Access Traffic Steering, Switching, and Splitting (aka *ATSSS*) is simpler to implement both on the UE and the mobile network side, lifting the specialized radio equipment burden for the operators, and reducing the exchange of radio control messages. What ATSSS essentially achieves, is to allow the establishment of a direct data path between the mobile device and the UPF over the 5G RAN and a WLAN, and allow for simultaneous traffic transmission and reception over both accesses. ATSSS is based on the principle of the Multi-Access PDU session (MA PDU) and the availability of multipath protocol extensions (i.e., MPTCP and MPQUIC) to aggregate network resources from a 3GPP and a non-3GPP access network (i.e., 5G NR

and WLAN, respectively). As its name reveals, this feature allows the mobile device to be connected to the 5G network, simultaneously over 5G NR and WLAN, and to steer, switch, or even split uplink and downlink data traffic over the two access networks. Leveraging this technique, technological isolation is eliminated, leading to mobile and fixed technology convergence. This way, fixed-access operators can provide 5G-based quality services to their end users over WLAN accesses. The ATSSS architecture diagram, as specified by 3GPP [7], is depicted in *Figure 5* below.

To support this functionality, the mobile device currently needs, in case of MPTCP, to be provided with a customized version of its operating system (OS) to incorporate the multipath extensions of TCP transport layer protocol. Deploying MPQUIC does not require OS modifications, but the application needs to be appropriately configured to support this multipath functionality. This allows the device to use its available interfaces (i.e., the cellular and the Wi-Fi) concurrently, to send and receive data traffic. In the same way, on the network side, UPF needs to be equipped with a multipath-capable proxy to be able to combine the incoming UL traffic before routing it to the internet and distribute the DL traffic over the available access paths. How the UL and DL traffic is distributed over the available access paths, is controlled by the network which derives and enforces the necessary policy and traffic distribution rules on the UE and the UPF; the ATSSS rules are provided by the network and are applied on the UE side, and the N4 rules on the UPF side, respectively. Various traffic distribution options are available in the context of ATSSS, allowing for traffic load-balancing over the available access paths, active and standby path configuration, traffic duplication, or even traffic routing over the path which experiences the smallest delay.

ATSSS is expected to serve as a basis for future networks, and further enhancements on this feature are envisioned, in order to realize the stringent and diverse 6G requirements, and provide ubiquitous connectivity. As it will be further analyzed within the rest of the current, as well as in the remaining sections, ATSSS is currently undergoing significant enhancements, seeking for example to support an additional 3GPP access network (DualSteer - Section V), thus providing the possibility for future mobile handsets to be connected to two cellular, as well as to a Wi-Fi network simultaneously. This will allow the provision of any kind of service, whatever its requirements; be it seamless connectivity during mobility by leveraging combinations of terrestrial and satellite 5G NR access networks, increased data rates through traffic aggregation from multiple networks, as well as service differentiation across the available accesses; all these without significant equipment investments from operators.

Figure 5: Non-roaming architecture for 5G Core Network with untrusted non-3GPP access.

B. ATSSS with Offloaded Non-3GPP Access (ATSSS-OF)

The legacy ATSSS architecture (Figure 5), as specified up until 3GPP Rel-18 and presented earlier in subsection A, requires the use of the *Non-3GPP InterWorking Function (N3IWF)* which is a Network Function (NF) acting as a network gateway that enables a device to register and securely exchange NAS signalling with the 5GC over an untrusted non-3GPP access network (e.g., using a WLAN). An alternative to this architecture could be a solution which eliminates the use of N3IWF without compromising network security. We hereby propose such an alternative solution in which, contrary to the legacy ATSSS, N3IWF is eliminated, and the UE does not register to the 5GC over the non-3GPP access path; instead, it registers only via the 3GPP access (e.g., via the 5G NR). This enhancement, named *ATSSS with Offloaded Non-3GPP Access (ATSSS-OF)*, requires the UE to initially register to the 5GC over an available 3GPP access, so that a N1 connection is established with AMF, and subsequent NAS signalling can be securely exchanged between the two. The proposed architecture is depicted in Figure 6 below. During the registration procedure over the 3GPP access, the UE is informed whether the network supports the *ATSSS-OF* feature and, in case it does, the UE may later include this indication within the MA PDU session establishment request message, which is also sent over the 3GPP access path, to indicate its preference to support this feature. During the MA PDU session establishment, the UE is expected to also indicate that it supports the MPQUIC steering functionality. The network, upon receiving the MA PDU session establishment request message with the multi-access offloading indication, derives the appropriate policy rules which determine how the UL and DL traffic should be routed across the 3GPP and the offloaded non-3GPP access. The network reserves the necessary resources as usual, with the only change being the reservation of a public IP address in the UPF, so that UPF can be reachable by the UE over the non-3GPP access. Upon successful MA PDU session establishment with offloaded non-3GPP access path support, the UE can establish a

MPQUIC connection with the UPF, and this connection should be established over the 3GPP access, for the network to be able to associate each MPQUIC connection with a QoS flow. Subsequently, the UE establishes an IP tunnel over HTTP with the UPF, which is used for “proxying IP in HTTP” traffic [12]. From this point onwards, the UE and the UPF can exchange data traffic via the 3GPP access path over the established MPQUIC connection and the IP tunnel. When at some point the UE decides to add an offloaded non-3GPP access path to the MPQUIC connection established over the 3GPP access, it leverages existing QUIC protocol functionality to validate the new path (i.e., using `PATH_CHALLENGE` frame exchange over the non-3GPP access). After successful validation, the UPF includes the new path (offloaded non-3GPP access) to the already established MPQUIC connection, and UL and DL data traffic can be exchanged between the UE and the UPF via either path of the MPQUIC connection; that is, either via the 3GPP or via the non-3GPP access.

The use of the MPQUIC protocol, with its inherent TLS encryption mechanism, guarantees integrity and confidentiality protection, enabling secure, authenticated, and authorized access to the 5GC via the public IP address exposed by UPF. This way 5G-quality services can be delivered to the UE without requiring the presence of N3IWF. While such a solution would speed up and ease network deployments, it entails a drawback. NAS signalling needs to be initiated and maintained only over the 3GPP access path, the absence of which (i.e., in case of access failure or UE’s poor signal), requires the whole session to be released. This solution is a typical trade-off example, on how a simplification in the network architecture comes at the cost of absence of control over the non-3GPP access path, and the network relying solely on the 3GPP access for normal session operation. This is why 3GPP might need some more time to reconsider such solutions in the context of 6G studies.

Figure 6: New ATSSS architecture using Offloaded Non-3GPP access.

IV. QUIC FOR NAS OVER NON-3GPP

As stated earlier, for the ATSSS functionality to normally operate, 3GPP has specified the N3IWF network function. This new function allows untrusted non-3GPP access networks offering connectivity services (e.g., WLAN access networks) to integrate to the 5G core network (5GC) and take advantage of the various capabilities and features it provides (i.e., network slicing, QoS differentiation, GBR, low latency, increased security, and many more). To achieve this integration with no security compromise, N3IWF serves as a secure gateway to and from the network. Before a device can connect to the 5GC over e.g., a WLAN access network using a Wi-Fi access point, an initial authentication procedure needs to take place and an appropriate N3IWF is selected. All subsequent NAS signalling exchanged between the UE and the network via the N3IWF, is conveyed through an IPsec tunnel which is established between the UE and N3IWF, before the latter one relays the UE NAS protocol messages to the network, and vice versa. To better understand N3IWF's role, its position within the 5G network architecture is depicted in *Figure 5* [7].

The establishment of an IPsec tunnel [8] for the secure transport of control plane messages induces an additional burden on the UE side. This is because the IPsec (operating in tunnel mode) needs to encrypt the whole packet before its transmission and encapsulate it within a new packet which is prepended an IPsec header. This procedure is complex and inefficient for two reasons. First, it diminishes the goodput since bandwidth is consumed for conveying the extra IPsec headers; this might not be obvious for large packets, but for small packets it imposes a significant overhead. In addition, the mobile device needs to consume additional resources to maintain the tunnel and reform the packets to be transmitted (respectively received) in the way described above. This

procedure may incur significant energy impact, draining the device battery faster for less data comprising the useful payload.

To optimize this procedure, we propose a solution which leverages the QUIC protocol for the transport of control plane messages between the UE and the N3IWF, eliminating the use of the more resource intensive IPsec tunneling. The QUIC protocol, standardized by IETF, is operating on top of UDP and provides a secure connection between end hosts, since it inherently supports TLS. QUIC also supports stream multiplexing, making it ideal for conveying HTTP/3 traffic and can be easily accommodated to the 5G Service Based Architecture (SBA). It is also equipped with a retransmission mechanism on the QUIC layer, rather than the transport layer, allowing the transport layer protocol stack to continue its normal operation in case one of the streams experiences packet losses. Our proposed solution envisions a simplified control plane protocol stack architecture which is based on the QUIC protocol and is depicted in *Figure 7* below.

Using this candidate protocol stack architecture, a UE can establish a preliminary QUIC connection with N3IWF, and exchange initial NAS messages using a stream on this QUIC connection. When N3IWF receives the common N3IWF key which is derived and sent by AMF, this initial QUIC connection can be released, and a new QUIC connection can be established between the UE and the N3IWF, following the successful mutual authentication of the two, using the derived N3IWF key. Then, all subsequent NAS messages can be exchanged via the new QUIC connection using stream mode. This provides a more efficient way to convey NAS signalling over the Non-3GPP access path, simplifying and optimizing the ATSSS functionality, while conserving resources both on the UE and at the network side.

Figure 7: QUIC-based non-3GPP access -- Control plane protocol stack.

V. DUAL-STEER SOLUTION BASED ON ATSSS

An additional requirement, known as *DualSteer* functionality, has been identified within 3GPP's Rel-19 studies (Stage 2 - *FS MASSS* Study Item). The idea behind the *DualSteer* study [13][14], was to capitalize on the capabilities an additional 3GPP access network can provide, be it additional bandwidth which is translated into increased throughput, or extended coverage through satellite access (i.e., with 5G NR NTN) in areas where terrestrial access availability is either scarce or not viable; all these on the basis of session continuity for the end user by providing, in essence, omnipresent connectivity with seamless handovers.

To support this new functionality, 3GPP seeks to unveil solutions which enable a mobile device to be connected to the 5GC simultaneously over two different 3GPP access networks, and over an additional non-3GPP access path. Based on this requirement, we hereby propose a candidate solution which is contributing to the network evolution towards an all-encompassing network, realizing ubiquitous connectivity.

Our proposed solution builds upon, and extends ATSSS, so as to support future mobile handsets to connect to the 5GC over two different 3GPP access networks of any Access Type, such as 5G NR dual- Terrestrial (TN) and/or Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTN), allowing also for multiple Radio Access Type (RAT) combinations (i.e., 5G NR TN + 5G NR NTN, or 5G NR NTN + LTE TN, etc.). This ultimately allows for resilience in case of poor signal quality or connectivity failures, and for even higher data rates, by combining two 3GPP access networks (i.e., two different 5G networks which could even belong to different PLMNs), and an additional non-3GPP access network (e.g., a WLAN). This way the mobile device can be simultaneously connected to and operate over three access paths, benefiting from higher throughput, robust and ubiquitous coverage.

Based on this principle, we propose a solution which addresses the aforementioned requirement, extending the ATSSS functionality, and providing the means to support ubiquitous multi-access connectivity. *Figure 8* illustrates the high-level architectural approach, depicting how a *DualSteer*-capable device can simultaneously be connected to and exchange traffic over three access paths. Note that the figure depicts an example on how a *DualSteer*-capable device can be connected to an additional non-terrestrial access network (NR NTN) belonging to a different PLMN (i.e., 3GPP path #2). However, the proposed solution is also applicable in cases where the two 3GPP access networks reside within the same PLMN.

On the technical details of the proposed solution, the main idea is to extend the MA PDU session, to support, besides a 3GPP access path and a non-3GPP access path, as currently specified within the legacy ATSSS (depicted in *Figure 8* with the red and green lines respectively), also an external access path (blue line in the figure). The MA PDU session is a logical

association between the UE and the Data Network (DN) and is essentially used to help the network reserve the necessary resources for the multipath communication and maintain session-specific information of the connected device. The *DualSteer* (DS) device first registers normally with PLMN-1 and PLMN-2. It can subsequently establish a single-access PDU session with PLMN-1 which is considered an "external access path". Later, when the DS device needs to establish a MA PDU session as dictated by the User Route Selection Policy rules (URSP), it provides an indication to the network (5GC in PLMN-2) that it can support an external access path over PLMN-1, which terminates at the UPF of PLMN-2 (anchor UPF). If PLMN-2 authorizes the use of an external access path to be supported in the MA PDU session, it reserves the necessary resources for both the DS device and the anchor UPF, and provides the device with the MPTCP proxy information (public IP address/port of anchor UPF in PLMN-2). This way, all UL traffic sent by the DS device via the external access path over PLMN-1, reaches the MPTCP proxy which is deployed within the UPF in PLMN-2. The MPTCP protocol provides the means to associate an additional subflow (i.e., the subflow over PLMN-1) with an existing MPTCP connection (established e.g., over PLMN-2). The MPTCP connection, which initially comprises two subflows, corresponding to the 3GPP access and the non-3GPP access of PLMN-2, can then be extended to include also an additional subflow over the external access path of PLMN-1.

Summarizing the technical details provided above, the core idea behind this solution is to extend the legacy ATSSS functionality by reusing the existing MA PDU session principle, and just adding, in the MA PDU session establishment request message, an indication to support an "external access path". This way we use the MA PDU session as a means to derive the appropriate policy rules (ATSSS rules) which are to be later enforced by the UE, considering the presence of an additional external path. When the UE is instructed by the extended ATSSS rules to send data traffic over the external access path, the initial single access PDU session (SA PDU) established over the external access in PLMN-1 is still used. Then the UPF in PLMN-1 is just forwarding the UL data traffic to the anchor UPF in PLMN-2. The respective procedure takes place in the DL direction, according to the N4 rules enforced by the anchor UPF in PLMN-2.

The DS device can be a dual-USIM UE or a device comprising two UEs; this solution is expected to accommodate both device-internal architectural options. This innovative contribution serves as a typical example on how we can prepare the ground for ubiquitous connectivity with minimum impact on existing NFs, by extending the existing ATSSS functionality. It is then up to the operator's policy to derive the appropriate ATSSS rules that determine how the UL and DL data traffic will be distributed among the available paths.

Figure 8: DualSteer solution based on ATSSS and using an external access path.

VI. TECHNICAL REALIZATION

In parallel with the architectural enhancements which are laying the ground for future multi-connectivity services, some initial implementation attempts have already commenced, with universities and research institutions to be providing the first ATSSS-compliant solutions. The EU-funded research project 6G-SANDBOX is envisioning an experimentation facility where fixed, 5G, and non-terrestrial networks will be fully integrated, offering an experimentation platform for 6G multi-connectivity use cases [15]. The ENVELOPE research project, which is also under the SNS-JU umbrella and seeks to provide advanced solutions for Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM), focuses on the implementation of an adaptive ATSSS-like solution, allowing reconfiguration by the vertical [16].

While the time interval between the end of a 3GPP release and the appearance of the first commercial products incorporating any 3GPP-specified feature (including ATSSS) is around three years, the core ATSSS-enabling protocols (i.e., MPTCP, MPQUIC, etc.) are already available, allowing for further tuning and enhancements of the various multi-access techniques and packet scheduling algorithms. Significant effort has been devoted in designing and implementing optimized packet schedulers, e.g., in the context of MPTCP, each one following a different approach to tackle known optimization problems and increase the overall performance; be it throughput maximization, HoL (Head-of-Line blocking) minimization [17], or even diminishing flow completion time [18].

Capitalizing on the research advancements in the multi-connectivity domain, guided by the 3GPP specifications, and particularly ATSSS, the initial multi-connectivity protocols and platforms are already available to accommodate the inaugural 6G use cases, serving as a basis for experimentation and further optimization.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

As stated by multiple 6G associations and research institutions, as well as operators' and governments' vision on 6G, there is expected to be a significant uplift in the network requirements, and any future enhancements are anticipated to

build upon and be compliant with 5G-Advanced. New use cases and network capabilities have been identified, such as Native AI, immersive experience, interconnection of the physical and digital world, integrated sensing and communications, and ubiquitous connectivity, to name a few. Through this work, we tried to analyze the various techniques which could aggregate bandwidth to provide increased throughput, but this is not the only factor as we pave the way toward 6G. A fully connected world, as envisioned in 6G, demands ubiquitous and resilient connectivity. In this direction, the multi-connectivity options already available in literature and specified in standards, are expected to be further enhanced and to play a vital role in achieving this objective.

Based on this necessity, we hereby proposed three enhancements which are expected to be discussed and possibly adopted in the 6G network architecture; i) the ATSSS-Offloaded (*ATSSS-OF*) alternative architecture which eliminates the use of N3IWF on the non-3GPP access path; ii) the enhancement of ATSSS with the use of the QUIC protocol to convey NAS signalling to the 5GC over Non-3GPP access; and iii) a candidate solution for DualSteer, which also extends ATSSS and enables a multi-access capable device to connect to an additional 3GPP access network, with all the advantages this entails.

The multi-connectivity techniques are anticipated to be further enhanced and even combinations of them and hybrid formats are expected to be adopted in 6G network architecture. The aforementioned innovative solutions remain in conceptual form and are expected to be discussed within the context of 3GPP [14] for further evaluation and possible adoption. A future direction would be a proof of concept where we could measure: i) the actual simplification in case of QUIC for non-3GPP access in terms of signalling time, and ii) experiments on the DualSteer part to understand how the device behaves, and what further optimization actions need to be applied to satisfy the stringent KPIs that 6G requests for.

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